

OPENING SESSION

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Opening of the conference “ The Modern City facing the Future”

The theme of the 6th International DOCOMOMO conference “The Modern City facing the Future” will give us a good opportunity to look on our own mirror. In that mirror we will see the past, we will see what has happened and the reality of today, we will see the intentions and the results of Modern Movement urbanism. If we look through that mirror and try to imagine the future, we see simulations of what is to come. It is important for us to look very critically in both ways at that mirror simultaneously, because it can lead us to some clues as to what could be the specific contribution of DOCOMOMO to appropriate cities of the future. This is not an easy task, because the images seen in that mirror are full of paradox. But as you will remember, DOCOMOMO is born out of the paradox how to keep the temporary, the transience of the past for future generations to be enjoyed.

So let us give it a try and first look back for a moment. The architect Cedric Price used the beautiful metaphor of the egg to describe the spatial development of cities (1). He compared the city from its early origins till the 19th century with a boiled egg, offering administrations, marked activities and inhabitants a cultured protection within the clear boundaries of the shell, against the untamed nature outside. However, due to rapid technological and economic improvements during the industrial revolution, cities began to spread their territories in concentric shapes, more or less like a fried egg. Transport systems criss-crossed living quarters, scattered around polluting factories, poverty and disease flourished, and an urban proletariat was born.

To counter this urban chaos idealistic architects at the beginning of the 20th century arrived at a

completely new tabula rasa approach, the Modern Movement. They thought they could see the future far ahead and planned new healthy and emancipated environments, fitting the aspirations and the requirements of a society which wasn't yet born. And planning, the rational and functional ordering of time-space became a panacea.

Separation of functions, the open organisation of space, the introduction of green in urban design and the high rise block became the innovative tools of housing modern man. Considering the 19th century conditions the proletariat used to live in, this new rational approach with its firm believe in a better future was indeed a great leap forwards. Many humane and beautiful examples emerged, all over the world.

However, particularly after World War II the qualitative ideas of the early innovators became standardised tools in the quantitative struggle of political agendas and the immediacy of speculation. Together with the hyperbolic increase in the demand for mobility, this automatically led to the unforeseen, the unexpected. Urban plans, regional plans and national plans succeeded each other in ever faster speed, trying to cope with the acceleration of changing demands and an unstoppable compulsion for improvement.

This rapidly changing realities showed again a new notion of the city. So next to Cedric Price's fried egg we are now served the scrambled eggs. These new cities are perceived as part of a set of relationships, spanning from the global to the national, the regional and to the local, with overlapping social, physical and digital networks.

But there is more. Information technology offers the possibility to be present and act at any place on the globe and be at home at the same time.

This in turn introduces yet again a completely different type of space-time, simultaneously yet incompatible with the traditional Newtonian type of time-space as represented in the boiled egg, the fried egg and the scrambled egg.

At the same time acceleration and delay, as well as increase and decrease of scale occur, where as simulation and reality merge into one.

Rem Koolhaas prophesised in his book *S, M, L, XL*, that we move towards, I quote: “The generic city, the city liberated from the captivity of center from the straight jacket of identity. The generic city is nothing but a reflection of present need and present ability. It is a city without history... If it gets too small it just expands. If it gets too old it just selfdestructs and renews. It is superficial like a Hollywood studio lot, it can produce a new identity every Monday morning... The great originality of the generic city is to abandon what doesn't work... to break up the blacktop of idealism with the jackhammers of realism and to accept

whatever grows in its place. In that sense the generic city accommodates both the primordial and the futuristic. ...But its most dangerous and most exhilarating discovery is that planning makes no difference whatsoever" End of quote.

Well, there you are. This is what one of the worlds most avantgarde and influential architects of today is telling us. Identity and historic layers are a waste of time and planning makes no difference whatsoever.

As you will understand, I tried very hard to have Koolhaas here at our conference as one of our key note speakers. But alas, due to having won the Pritzker Prize recently his diary didn't allow him in the end.

So where do we stand, we as DOCOMOMO should ask ourselves if planning of the city in the sense of the Modern Movement is impossible, because its consists of thousands of incompatible coordination systems, how will we manage the different layers of speed and spatial meaning simultaneously, and how do we find balances between order and chaos for our future cities?

One thing we do know. However digitalised, fragmented, nomadic or multicultural we have become, an ecological and social spatial equilibrium will always remain a necessity. Besides the importance of emancipation, of self determination and participation, the need of belonging and intimacy, of historic and local identity will be as relevant in the future as it was in the past. And perhaps even more so in a hyper-dynamic and secular era like ours.

This conference will show, that apart from the stereotype and true criticism about the modern city, there are also many valuable qualities, which are or could be of vital importance to our future.

Dear DOCOMOMO friends let us be open-minded and critical about the urban past of Modern Movement and about our own specific contribution to the future. We should ask ourselves two main questions:

1. What can we learn from the past experiences with modern cities? and
2. What are the key elements of existing modern cities that we should keep in one or another way for future generations, why do we want to keep them and how?

Let's try to find answers to these questions in a spirit of optimism, that characteristic quality of the pioneers of the Modern Movement. The idea that the city can contribute to the happiness of all; something that can't be left solely to marked forces or short-term political agendas. It very much needs the idealistic input from all of us as well. Just think of the social injustice around us, the population boom and the ecological urgency.

I sincerely hope that the choice of speakers and the contribution to the debates by everybody will lead us to some clues. I wish you a very productive conference.